

Geothermal activities at the KTB deep crustal lab (Windischeschenbach, Germany)

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Abstract

The site of the Kontinentale Tiefbohrung (KTB), Windischeschenbach, is one of the best characterised locations of continental upper crust worldwide. The two superdeep KTB boreholes represent a unique in situ underground research laboratory in Europe, allowing research into the sustainable utilisation of the crystalline subsurface for the energy and heat transition.

The GEOREAL experiment aimed at hydraulically stimulating the fractured crystalline metamorphic basement rocks at 4 km depth while minimising the potential risk of induced seismicity by real-time control of injection parameters. The KTB infrastructure allowed to inject 600 m³ of water during 6-15 November 2023 into the 4 km deep KTB pilot hole, while the main borehole (200 m distant at the surface) was used for seismic monitoring.

Fluid injection took place through/bypassing the stuck packer pressurising the open borehole section at the depth interval of 3.85–4 km. Flow rates were variable (10-220 l/min). The GEOREAL experiment had to be stopped prematurely due to a leak in the casing cement. No induced microseismic events were detected. Pressure data, monitored at the well head of both KTB borehole, was analysed in conjunction with recordings from a year-long injection experiment into the same formation performed in 2004-2005. The hydraulic parameters show similar values as previously obtained. The observations provide more detail on the hydraulic connection at depth between both boreholes. A new drawdown test is underway to confirm these findings, substantiating the potential of petrothermal research at the KTB superdeep crustal lab after 30 years of operation.

Introduction

Geothermal energy has the potential to supply about a quarter of the heat demand in Germany (about 300 terawatt hours per year). This does not include the potential for petrothermal deep energy systems (EGS), which could contribute even more in the long term (see Roadmap Deep Geothermal Energy for Germany). Therefore, the successful development of petrothermal resources can make an important contribution to the energy and heat transition in Germany. In most parts of Germany, crystalline rock is found in the deep underground, with similar or more suitable geothermal conditions to those found at the Kontinentale Tiefbohrung (KTB) near Windischeschenbach, NE Bavaria (Anikiev et al., 2019), making the KTB an ideally suited research site for studying petrothermal reservoirs.

The two superdeep boreholes KTB main hole (KTB-HB) with a final depth of 9.1 km and the adjacent 4 km-deep KTB pilot hole (KTB-VB) represent a unique in situ underground research laboratory (URL) in Europe (Harms and Kück, 2016). The boreholes provide physical access to a petrothermal fluid reservoir with fluid temperatures of 100-190° C.

Detailed knowledge of the crustal structure around the KTB site has been achieved during decades of pre- and post-drilling crustal exploration experiments (Buske, 1999; Harjes et al., 1997; Hloušek and Buske, 2016; Rabbel et al., 2004; Stiller, 1991). In particular, repeated seismic, electrical, hydraulic, and geophysical measurements have (1) allowed tracking of natural and injection-induced temporal and spatial microearthquake clusters, revealing stress relaxation, and the so-called "Kaiser (memory) effect", where previously activated regions show reduced activity in subsequent experiments (Baisch

et al., 2002; Kummerow et al., 2004), (2) aimed at detecting changes in reflection amplitudes due to fluid injection (Beilecke et al., 2010) and (3) allowed for imaging of high-conductivity, graphitized shear zones and a self-potential anomaly.

However, geophysical monitoring was mostly completed by 2006, when research activities ceased at the KTB (Harms and Kück, 2016). During the last 20 years of KTB's operation, the KTB infrastructure served mainly as a testing facility for instrumentation (e.g., within the ICDP*) and operational site for commercial cable seasoning. In the framework of the GEOREAL hydraulic stimulation experiment in 2023, passive seismic, hydraulic and temperature monitoring were restarted.

The main goal of the GEOREAL project was to stimulate the fractured crystalline rock at 4 km depth to investigate hydro-mechanical processes in metamorphic basement rocks while minimizing induced seismic risk through adjusting injection parameters in near-real time (Boese et al., *subm.*). A total of 600 m³ of fresh water was injected into the surrounding of a well-characterized fault zone (named SE2) at 4 km depth in KTB-VB with variable flow rates, ranging from 10 to 220 l/min between 6–15 November 2023. Pressure records were obtained at the well heads of KTB-VB and KTB-HB, the latter of which was also used for downhole microseismic monitoring. The experiment had to be stopped earlier than planned due to technical problems. No microseismic events were detected during the injection. Hydraulic data were analysed in comparison with results from a year-long injection experiment into the same formation in 2004-2005 (Kummerow et al., 2004). These suggest that no significant permeability changes have occurred in the SE2 fault zone over two decades, indicating that fracture healing does not play a major role in the reservoir.

A hydraulic response in the KTB-HB to injection in KTB-VB was not observed in the pressure records, likely because the volume of 600 m³ of injected water was insufficient to displace enough formation fluid nor induce a significant pressure pulse in the surrounding of KTB-HB. Previous experiments in 1992, 2000 and 2004 inferred a direct hydraulic connection between the KTB boreholes below 5 km depth during drilling and a weak hydraulic communication around the leakage around 5.4 km depth in KTB-HB and low transmissivity paths off the SE2 fault zone after casing of KTB-HB. To further investigate hydraulic communication between the KTB boreholes, drawdown tests have been started in KTB-HB. We report on pressure measurements since 2023 before and during infill/drawdown tests in KTB-HB. Fluid movement at depth is detected by temperature and fluid logging results, which have been regularly conducted since the completion of KTB-HB. The most recent measurements from Aug 2025 are compared to all previous results and are summarized below.

The depth range of interest regarding the observed fluid flow was seismically active during the KTB2000 injection experiment, when a fluid volume of 4,000 m³ was injected into the KTB-HB wellhead (Baisch et al., 2002; Bohnhoff et al., 2004). A total of 2,800 seismic events ($M_L \leq 0.7$) were detected of which 237 were localised. Events clustered at distinct hypocentral depth intervals (~ 3.3 km, ~ 5.4 km and ≥ 8 km depth, respectively; Baisch et al., 2002), but the majority ($\sim 80\%$) of the microearthquakes was concentrated at 5.1-5.4 km depth. A casing leak could be confirmed by logging at this depth range. Previous studies by Baisch et al., 2002, Bohnhoff et al., 2004, Vavryčuk et al., 2008, and Rothert et al., 2003 showed a fracture network of steeply dipping faults with diffusion values of ≥ 0.004 m²/s that also hosted the largest induced KTB earthquake (of $M_L \sim 1.2$). This fracture network is of particular interest with respect to geothermal investigations due to the ambient temperature of $\sim 150^\circ\text{C}$. A reinvestigation of the induced seismicity at this depth was started using a template-matching procedure to detect more microearthquakes in the continuous seismic records. An example cluster of detected events resulting from this investigation is presented.

Data

1. Temperature and fluid resistivity logs

Temperature measurements in KTB-HB have been performed every 2–8 years to depths of at least 5.1 km. For most logging campaigns these temperature logs were combined with fluid resistivity and pressure measurements (Table 1). Measurements until 1998 were performed using an analog Schlumberger sonde, while later measurements were obtained using Antares sensors. To better visualise long-term temperature changes, we use the temperature measurements from 28 Jan 1998 as a reference for the least drilling-disturbed temperature profile and subtract this temperature profile from each subsequent logging profile. The reference log shows a constant gradient of 29 °C/km.

The two logging results in 2000 were obtained before (May, brown) and after (December, purple in Fig. 2) the KTB2000 injection experiment. Table 1 provides details on the selected logging campaigns investigated further.

Table 1: Details of selected logging campaigns in KTB-HB.

Log date	Temperature	Fluid resistivity	Pressure	Maximal depth [km]
28 Jan 1998	X	-	-	8.55
May 2000	X	X	X	5.9
11 Dec 2000	X	X	X	6.9
4&5 Jan 2005	X	X	X	5.8
23 Feb 2010	X	X	X	6.0
Apr 2017	X	-	X	5.1
13 Jun 2025	X	X	X	5.08

2. Fracture system

A reinvestigation of the induced seismicity at ~5 km depth was started using a template-matching procedure to search the approximately three months of continuous seismic data from up to 20 short period stations in the direct surrounding of the KTB (Figure 1). For this the open-source software *EQcorrscan* (Chamberlain et al., 2017) was applied which is based on the cross-correlation method. Using the waveforms of 136 identified microearthquakes during the KTB-2000 experiment at 5-5.6 km depth as templates, a total of 1,500 similar signals with low signal-to-noise ratio were detected. An example of detections in cluster 3, which started on 23 Aug 2000 and was active throughout the whole monitoring period is presented. Only 8 events are listed in the original event catalogue while the new detections expand the catalogue tenfold.

Figure 1: Station network used for template matching procedure for a re-evaluation of the KTB2000 induced seismicity.

3. Fluid volume changes in KTB-HB

Drawdown tests at different depths during the drilling of KTB-HB resulted in flow back through several distinct fracture zones as identified by repeated logging. The last and largest drawdown of 513 m in 1992 and subsequent cement injection for casing cementation in KTB-HB were associated with volumetric changes of 30 m³ each, causing significant pressure changes of up to 0.05 bar in KTB-VB (see Boese et al., subm. and references therein for a detailed discussion). By unlogging fractures from drilling residuals inflow through a casing leakage at this depth was enabled through the large pressure difference between formation and borehole fluid pressures. A direct hydraulic connection between the KTB boreholes below 5 km depth was inferred (Kessels and Kück, 1995), and a likely candidate seemed to be the fracture system identified at ~5.2 km depth (Baisch et al., 2002).

During the GEOREAL experiment, the fluid column of KTB-HB was filled up to the wellhead on 31 Oct 2023. Afterwards, the fluid level lowered to its' static level of ~20 m over three months. This was monitored by a pressure sensor at 35 m depth. The static water level below surface (measured on 22 Jan 2024) was associated with a pressure of 2.11 bar given the depth of the pressure sensor. We fit the observed pressure decay by an exponential function with time t (in seconds) of type

$$a \exp(-b t) + p_0, \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where p_0 is the pressure measured by the sensor for static water level and a and b are constants obtained.

To test the pressure response to water removal a drawdown test was performed on 21 August 2025 and the water level was lowered by 20 m. The pressure recording failed during the first month. When

it was restarted, we could monitor for two weeks before other borehole activities prevented further pressure monitoring. Nevertheless, the short record obtained could also be fit using the exponential function with negative parameter a , and will be validated in a repeated drawdown test in the future.

A further refilling of KTB-HB to the wellhead was initiated on 21 Oct 2025 and has been monitored since using a pressure sensor at a depth of 88 m. The initial pressure corresponds to 9.47 bar but the final static water level has not yet been reached.

Results

Logging results from KTB-HB obtained over the last 30 years allow for trends and features to be identified in the temperature and fluid composition (salinity). While in general absolute temperature changes are small in the long-term depth profiles, large changes in mud resistivities are observed between different logging campaigns (Fig. 2). The borehole fluid of the initial drilling mud composition was completely changed by fluid injection experiments in 1994 and 2000 and further diluted by repeated fresh water infilling in the uppermost part over the last 10 years. The largest temperature differences between logging campaigns are seen above 2,000 m and below 5,000 m depth. While above 2,000 m persistent absolute temperature anomalies of small amplitude exist, the most interesting large temperature deviations are seen at $\geq 5,400$ m depth for the post-injection log in Dec 2000. The most recent logging campaign revealed some remarkable differences compared to previous logs: The temperature measured in 2025 is about 1°C higher in temperature for depths $>2,500$ m than previously. Fluid resistivities are more variable throughout the whole depth range between different logging campaigns. The most recent log exhibits fluid resistivities above 1,880 m which are significantly different to previous measurements, eventually reaching comparable values below 2,040 m depth. The resistivity anomalies seen below 4,656 m are a new feature of significant amplitude that are not expressed in the temperature log and will require confirmation in future resistivity logs.

The effect of the KTB2000 injection experiment can be clearly seen in the pre- and post-injection logs. The most extensive fluid resistivity changes occurred in the depth range 5,350 to 5,800 for the Dec 2000 log at the depth of the confirmed casing leakage. An interesting observation is that temperature and fluid resistivity anomalies are slightly offset in depth.

Figure 2: (left) Residual temperature profile with depth for logging campaigns between with 2000 and 2025 with respect to the reference temperature log obtained in 1998 and (right) fluid resistivity logs obtained for the same logging campaigns.

Newly detected microearthquakes for one cluster obtained from eight templates are shown for two different stations in Figure 3. A total of 110 detections were obtained, but only the first 20 events in the cluster are shown. Clustering has been previously investigated by Baisch and Harjes (2003) who identified at least 25 multiplets of four to seven highly similar microearthquakes. While the new detections show many events with signal-to-noise ratios of one, and waveforms are characterised as a change in frequency rather than amplitude compared to the background noise, these new events are detected by on average 10 stations. We also note that the detections span the whole recording period of three months, while Baisch and Harjes (2003) report of shorter durations with the maximum multiplet span of 20 days. A re-analysis of the activated structures during the 2000 injection using these more extensive clusters is underway with the aim to gain new insight in the connectedness of identified individual structures at different depths as well as their spatio-temporal activation during fluid injection.

Figure 3: Example waveforms of detections obtained for two stations using the KTB2000 events as templates for a template matching analysis.

Pressure monitoring of two refill tests in KTB-HB as shown in Figure 4 exhibit a similar decay curve resulting from fluid level drops to static water level of ca. 20 m below surface. The pressure sensors during both tests were located at different depths resulting in different absolute pressures. Exponential fits to these pressure curves indicate that the response to refill is the main feature and barometric pressure changes are overprinting a small-amplitude deviation (c.f. Boese et al., *subm.*). The continuation of the ongoing test (as shown in top panel) will confirm whether the same pressure decay as previously observed will persist. The response to a drawdown of similar volume as the infill appears to have slightly different characteristics as shown schematically in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Pressure decay observed (top) in 2025 immediately following refilling of KTB-HB and (bottom) during GEOREAL one month after refilling of KTB-HB. The time scale displayed is the same to allow for comparison of the observed (black) and fit (coloured) decay curves.

The comparison of the exponential fit parameters to pressure decay versus increase in KTB-HB for similar volume of fluid added or removed, respectively, shows that a and b parameters (eq. 1) are larger for pressure decrease than for increase. As different short temporal parts of the 3-months long period (required to reach static water levels) are currently fit, and we do not yet know how good the fits really are, we will wait for the current refilling test to be completed before continuing with interpreting these pressure curves.

Figure 5: Comparison of exponential fitting function for refill-related pressure decrease and drawdown-related pressure increase.

Discussion

Two refill tests performed at the KTB-HB show similar behaviour in water level recovery to static water level. This likely indicates fluid inflow into fractures at depth, because recent logging results show no leakages down to a depth of 4,656 m. Downwards of this depth distinct anomalies in fluid resistivities are observed that are not seen in temperature. These new resistivity anomalies were not present in previous logging campaigns and could be explained by inflow into the borehole of fluids with higher salinity than the borehole fluid at these depths. A temperature effect may not be seen due to the long equilibration time of the borehole fluid to the surrounding rock mass, so that fluid flow is only seen due to compositional differences.

A fracture system at depths of ~5 km intersected by the KTB-HB has been identified through seismic events observed during the KTB2000 injection experiment. While the seismicity revealed clustered activity, no detailed spatio-temporal characterisation of the activated fractures and their interconnectedness was possible, partly because most events could only be identified in the waveforms recorded by a downhole seismometer. Using newly identified microseismic events of low signal-to-noise ratio from the continuous passive seismic dataset, not analysed before, we aim for a new characterisation of the spatio-temporal event distribution. There are currently five seismic clusters resolved with significantly different sizes and durations.

At the KTB-VB extensive flushing of the borehole (wall) was necessary to obtain reliable permeability estimates of the intersected fracture system at 4 km depth. The seismic evaluation of the GEOREAL experiment shows no reactivation of faults in this deformation zone. This may be due to the low

injection volume, low diffusivity, or the Kaiser effect. Nevertheless, the permeability obtained two decades ago could be confirmed by GEOREAL, suggesting that these fractures remained open.

Whether permeability of the ~5 km deep fracture system intersected by KTB-HB has changed with time is currently an open question. A ~500 m fluid column drawdown test in 1992 stimulated an inflow of ~30 m³ in KTB-HB and likely unclogged these fractures. To obtain a similar effect given the different borehole fluid now in KTB-HB at least 300 m of fluid column have to be removed. We plan to perform such a drawdown test to stimulate fluid movement along these fractures in the near future.

Conclusions and outlook

The KTB deep crustal laboratory enables EGS research (such as GEOREAL) that complements current major research projects elsewhere such as the FORGE project (USA), the ST1 Helsinki geothermal project (Finland), the Haute Sorne geothermal project (Switzerland), and the GEOLAB project (Germany), providing important information on the sustainable use of the subsurface in Germany in the context of the energy and heat transition.

The main borehole KTB-HB has been the subject of many investigations and is still an instrumentation testing, cable seasoning and logging reference measurement site since the end of the active experimental phase at KTB in 2006. An extensive fracture system in the depth range 5-5.6 km depth has been identified with ambient temperatures of $\geq 150^{\circ}\text{C}$. Fluid flow along these fractures can likely be activated through removing a certain fluid volume through pumping at the top of KTB-HB.

We will expand on previous drawdown test in the KTB-HB to gain further insights regarding fluid inflow into the borehole but also the complex flow paths between the two deep KTB boreholes. We plan to periodically remove water in the upper section of the borehole to further stimulate inflow of formation fluid into KTB-HB at depth and combine this with fluid sampling in the vicinity of the identified casing leakage.

Long-term pressure observations in both boreholes are also planned, especially given the fact that KTB-VB has been identified as a particular strain sensitive borehole (areal strain sensitivity of 0.16-0.19 hPa/ne according to Schulze et al., 2000) in the open-hole borehole section.

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